

DEVELOPMENT OF COMPETENCE IN THE ANALYSIS OF CHILDREN'S WORKS OF ART IN FUTURE EDUCATOR- PEDAGOGICAL STUDENTS

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Abstract. The article talks about the current issues and importance of forming a culture of reading in preschool children, introducing them to fiction. The effect of keeping pace with the book on children's development is highlighted.

Keywords: literature, book culture, book reading, publication, society, spirituality, character, will, emotion.

INTRODUCTION

The prosperity of the nation and the development of the country depend on the reading level of the people, that is, their education. Namely, the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoev dated January 12, 2017 "On the establishment of a commission on the development of the system of printing and distribution of book products, increasing and promoting the culture of book reading and reading" and September 13 Decision PD-3271 "On the program of comprehensive measures to develop the system of publication and distribution of book products, increase and promote book reading and reading culture" showed that he has raised his role to a new level [1].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The main task of every person, every family, and society is to raise capable children, to raise them to become physically and mentally mature people, loyal to

their parents and the Motherland. Therefore, it is the main task to form children's interest in books for the first time.

The environment, parents, and educators have an important place in child education, and character, will, and emotions are formed from childhood. In this case, the importance of reading is incomparable in the formation of positive adjectives.

Raising a child requires responsibility. A responsible person always carefully plans his work, foresees its consequences in advance, and mobilizes all his strength and potential to achieve it.

There is a saying in our people: "If you don't remember what you miss, you will gradually forget it." Reading a book requires an example. If only reading was inherited. From the moment a child is born, every parent wants their child to succeed in life. But no matter how knowledgeable and talented we are, the question arises whether we can pass these things on to our children [3].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

"Interactive reading is not limited to the time parents spend together with their child near the book, but the essence of this process is the interaction of parents with the child." The reason is that psychologists say that children aged 7-10 go through a specific period of development. At this age, children are aware of their own inner intuition and consciousness. At the same time, the feelings of feeling like an adult and slowly evaluating and behaving are awakened. Therefore, the role of parents, teachers and mentors is very important for children at this age. Basically, there is mutual and deep trust in adults. Also, in this cycle, children develop their main energy resources and potential. He is mobile, very active, and his inner world, thoughts, and mind become like this. This cycle allows parents and teachers to take a genuine interest in each event.

In the "State requirements for the development of children of primary and preschool age", in the requirements for the development of the skills of reading

and teaching literature of preschool children, the child expresses interest in books and reading, and the expected results are as follows [4]:

3-4-year-old children have an understanding of books; asks adults to read books; reads age-appropriate books; determines the connection between pictures and words in the book; recognizes familiar fairy tale characters from pictures.

- 4-5-year-old children react to the story they listened to and ask questions to adults; can tell the main parts of the work he listened to based on the pictures; can say the name of the work after listening to an excerpt from a work of art; he knows by heart poems suitable for his age; uses the book carefully.

- 5-6 years old knows the first sound in a word; reads the book independently; distinguishes sounds; divides words into syllables; rhymes with words; uses a dialogical form of speech, asks questions; memorizes poems and reads expressively; knows the authors of favorite fiction, fairy tales and stories and their names; correctly uses the tonal means of expression; finds words related to letters.

- 6-7 years old tells other children the contents of the book they remember; uses simple and complex sentences in his speech; divides words into syllables; creates words from syllables using syllable cards; has an understanding of words, sounds, syllables, sentences; reads peshlavha, book titles, captions, etc.; knows the name of the genre of children's literature (tale, poem, story); knows the names of famous writers and poets.

Parents are preparing the ground for a bright future of their children based on the formation of a reading atmosphere in the family. This requires parents to correctly understand their moral duty to their children, to the nation, to form family relationships, and to educate them as independent thinking individuals.

The first and most important criterion of spirituality depends in many ways on the fact that each person becomes an educated, intellectually developed person.

It is known that reading is not defined only by reading a lot. It will be

realized only when good character, good manners, healthy worldview, healthy lifestyle, and social activity are formed through the books they read.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it can be said that the qualitative characteristics of the development of the motivational sphere of the future teacher-pedagogue student depend on the personal and professional direction, the direction of values. The motivational sphere of the person is determined by the activity. In order for the activity to be a component of development and self-development, it is important not only to deeply understand the nature of its content, but also to constantly improve the motivational side of the individual.

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